

BIR JINSLI BO‘LMAGAN ASOSDA YOTUVCHI UCH QATLAMLI PLITANING ICHKI ZO‘RIQISHINI BAHOLASHGA DOIR MASALANING MATEMATIK MODELLASHTIRILISHI

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***Annotatsiya.** Bir jinsli bo‘lmagan asosda yotuvchi uch qatlamli plitalardagi ichki zo‘riqish kuchlarini baholashga doir masala qaralgan. Guruntli asosning bir jinslimasligi chuqurlik bo‘yicha darajali qonuniyatga bo‘ysinuvchi o‘zgaruvchi deb olingan. Plitalar orasiga elastik to‘ldiruvchi qatlam joylashtirilgan. To‘ldiruvchi qatlamning plitalarga bosimi ularning egilishlari farqiga proporsional deb olingan. Amaliyotda ko‘p uchraydigan to‘plangan kuch ta‘siridagi uch qatlamli balka-plitalarning egilish tenglamalari keltirilgan. Masalani yechuvchi yopiq tenglamalar sistemasidan iborat matematik model yaratilgan.*

***Kalit so‘zlar:** Bir jinslimas, qatlamli, to‘plangan kuch, singulyarlik, kontakt shart, cho‘kish, sistema.*

Masalaning qo‘yilishi. Bir jinsli bo‘lmagan guruntli asosga jips joylashtirilgan ikki qatlamli plitalarni qaraymiz. Plitalar orasiga elastik qatlam joylashtirilgan bo‘lsin. Plitalar orasidagi elastik qatlamni to‘ldiruvchi qatlam deb nomlaymiz. To‘ldiruvchi qatlamni uchinchi qatlam deb tushunish mumkin. Yuqorida joylashgan plitaning simmetriya markazidagi bo‘ylama o‘q bo‘ylab amalda ko‘p uchraydigan to‘plangan P tashqi kuch qo‘yilganda plitalardagi ichki zo‘riqish kuchlarini aniqlash va baholash masalasini qaraymiz. Aytilgan uch qatlamli plita bilan asosning kontakt munosabatida plitalarning bo‘yi va eni bir xil $-b$ va $-2l$, balandliklari turlicha $-h_1, h_2$ bo‘lsin deb faraz qilamiz. Qaralayotgan konstruksiyadagi qatlamli plitadan bir birlik kesimidan iborat bo‘lakchasini olamiz. Bu bo‘lakcha yuqoridan simmetriya markaziga to‘plangan kuch qo‘yilgan uch qatlamli balka-plitalarni bildiradi. Shu sabab qaralayotgan masala uch qatlamli balka-plitalarning hisobiga oid masalaga keltiriladi.

Masalaning matematik modellashtirilishi

Quaylik maqsadida koordinatalar markazini uch qatlamli balka-plitalarning simmetriya markaziga joylashtiramiz. U holda asosning cho‘kishi balka-plitalarning egilishlari (salqiliklari) x o‘zgaruvchining funksiyalari bo‘lad [3,6,7].

Elastik bir jinsli bo‘lmagan asosning elastiklik moduli chuqurlik bo‘yicha darajali uzluksiz funksiya bo‘lib,

$$E = E_m y^m, \quad 0 \leq m < 1 \quad (1)$$

ko‘rinishidagi qonuniyatga ega bo‘lsin [1,2,5]. Bu yerda m -asosning bir jinslimaslik koeffitsiyenti; E_m - asosning mexanik parametrlaridan bog‘liq o‘zgarmas miqdor bo‘lib, quyidagi formula bilan aniqlanadi:

$$E_m = \frac{(m+3)[1-\nu_0(1+m)]E_0}{2(1-m^2)(1-\nu_0^2)r^m}. \quad (2)$$

Bu formulada ν_0 va E_0 - bir jinsli asosning Poisson koeffitsiyenti va elastiklik moduli; r - tajriba shtampi radiusi.

Garbunov-Pasadov nazariyasi asosida bir jinsli bo‘lmagan asosning $W(x)$ cho‘kishini reaktiv $p(x)$ bosimi bilan bog‘lovchi [4,5]

$$W(x) = \int_{-l}^l K(x,s)p(s) ds \quad (3)$$

formuladan foydalanamiz. Bu yerda singulyar integral yadrosi uchun guruntli asosning xususiyatlarini inobatga olib, quyidagini olamiz:

$$K(x,s) = \frac{\theta_m}{m} \frac{1}{|x-s|^m}. \quad (4)$$

Bu yerda

$$\theta_m = \frac{(1 - \nu_0^2) \sin \frac{\gamma\pi}{2} \Gamma[1 + (1 - \gamma + m)/2] \Gamma[1 + (1 + \gamma + m)/2]}{\pi(1 + m)E_m 2^{-1-m} \Gamma(m + 2)};$$

$$\gamma^2 = [1 - \nu_0(m + 1)](m + 1)(1 - \nu_0)^{-1};$$

$\Gamma(x)$ -Eylerning gamma funksiyasi.

Quyida joylashgan balka-plitaning egilishini $W_1(x)$ deb, yuqoridagisikini $W_2(x)$ deb belgilaymiz. To'ldiruvchi qatlamning balka-plitalarga bo'lgan $p_t(x)$ bosimini balka-plitalar egilishlari farqiga proporsional deb,

$$\lambda(W_1 - W_2) = p_t \quad (5)$$

ko'rinishda qabul qilamiz. Bu yerda λ – to'ldiruvchi qatlamning bikirlik koeffitsiyenti.

Qayd etilgan hisoblash sxemasiga muvofiq keltirilgan balka-plitalarning egilishlarini ifodalovchi differensial tenglamalarni quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$D_1 W_1^{IV} = p_t(x) - p(x), \quad D_2 W_2^{IV} = P - p_t(x)$$

yoki (5) tenglikni inobatga olsak

$$\left. \begin{aligned} D_2 W_2^{IV} &= P - \lambda(W_2 - W_1) \\ D_1 W_1^{IV} &= \lambda(W_2 - W_1) - p(x) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Bu yerda

$$D_1 = \frac{h_1^3 E_1}{R(1 - \nu_1^2)}, \quad D_2 = \frac{h_2^3 E_2}{R(1 - \nu_2^2)}.$$

E_1, E_2 va ν_1, ν_2 - mos ravishda birinchi va ikkinchi balka-plitalarning elastiklik moduli va Puasson koeffitsiyentlari.

Tashqi kuchning qo'yilishiga muvofiq quyidagi chegara shartlarning bajarilishi talab qilinadi:

1. Chetki $x = \pm l$ nuqtalarda:

$$W_1'' = W_2'' = W_1''' = W_2''' = 0. \quad (6)$$

2. Simmetriya markazi $x = 0$ da:

$$W_1' = W_2' = W_1''' = W_2''' = 0. \quad (7)$$

Quyidagi joylashgan balka-plitaning asosda jips yotishini, ya'ni balka-plita va asosning ikki tomonlama uzluksiz kontakt shartini

$$W(x) = W_1(x), \quad -l \leq x \leq l \quad (8)$$

ayniy tenglik shaklida olamiz.

Shunday qilib, qaralayotgan masala (3), (6), (8) tenglamalarni birgalikda (6), (7) chegara shartlarda yechishga keltiriladi. Keltirilgan integro-differensial tenglamalar sistemasi qaralayotgan masalaning yechimini aniqlovchi asosiy matematik tenglamalardan iboratdir. Tenglamalarni birgalikda qarab, simmetrik to'plangan kuch ta'siridagi uch qatlamli plitalarning egilishini bir jinsli bo'lmagan guruntli asosning reaktiv bosimi orqali ifodalovchi formulalar

aniqlanadi. Bu formulalar yordamida elastiklik nazariyasining tegishli qoidalariga asoslanib plitalarda ro‘y beradigan ichki zo‘riqish kuchlarini aniqlovchi ifodalarni olish mumkin bo‘ladi.

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